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Application of Data Analytics on Improvements in Standardized Visualization Test Scores

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ABSTRACT

Visualization skills have been identified as critical competence for success in STEM disciplines, particularly in engineering and technology fields. Several academic institutions in the United States implemented a policy to have first-year engineering students tested on such competence, and several initiatives to improve visualization skills have been implemented. A standardized visualization test (i.e., PSVT:R), which is widely accepted as indicator of visualization skills, is used as one of the indicators to evaluate students and it is the one used in this study. In this work we applied data analytics techniques to a dataset (N=185) to compare pre- and post-test scores, with the aim to identify factors in the PSVT:R test that are most influential in predicting score improvement. The PSVT:R standard test is a set of 30 questions that can be grouped in several subsets based on the number of manipulations that need to be performed in order to get to the correct answer for each question. In this study, a group of first-year engineering students were tested and three different pedagogical interventions were utilized. Results from this study, obtained by the application of data analytics techniques, confirmed previous conclusions for single-instance test scores and identified influential factors in a predictive model. Further, results show a level of similarity, but not fully consistent results, thus demonstrating the usefulness of data analytics in this type of analyses. The identification of influential factors (i.e., specific questions) in a predictive model for score improvement can aid in the definition of content needed in pedagogical interventions.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Spatial skills and STEM education

Spatial reasoning is important for success in many STEM fields. Spatial reasoning is defined as human ability to encode and maintain spatial information in working memory while transforming it (Carroll, 1993). There is a vast amount of research providing evidence for individual difference in spatial reasoning as well as evidence that spatial thinking skills can be improved through training and experience (Uttal & Cohen, 2012). Training is particularly important for incoming engineering students to develop strong spatial visualization skills early in an academic program, as many incoming engineering students need remediation in spatial visualization.

Higher education initiatives in the United States have been implemented to develop and enhance spatial visualization skills of engineering students. For example, one of the first programs, The EnVISION (Enhancing Visualization Skills-Improving Options aNd Success) project was introduced in 2007 to test and enhance the spatial visualization skills of incoming engineering and technology students. The EnVISION approach has been used by a variety of U.S. universities, including Michigan Technological University, Penn State, The Behrend College, Purdue University, University of Iowa, Virginia State University, and Virginia Tech. The EnVISION course is targeted to students who have been identified as needing remedial instruction. By helping students with low spatial visualization skills to success, particularly women as research shows that they are outperformed by their male peers on spatial related tasks (Voyer, 1995), the EnVISION project leaders hoped to improve the retention of these students in STEM disciplines and to enhance their success (Veurink et al., 2009). Comparing the pre-initiative and the post-initiative performance of students enrolled in remedial programs, measured by their scores in a standardized visualization test, serves as an indication of the effectiveness of the implemented initiative.

1.2 Measuring spatial skills

In the United States engineering educators typically use spatial visualization tests to screen first-year engineering (FYE) for spatial ability. There is no definitive spatial visualization test, therefore variety of assessments, including the Purdue Spatial Visualization Test with Rotations (PSVT:R; Guay, 1976), the Mental Cutting Test, the Revised Minnesota Paper Form Board Test, and the Differential Aptitude Test are used to screen FYE students for spatial ability (Maeda, Yoon, Kim-Kang, & Imbrie, 2013). While useful in identifying students, who would benefit from remedial spatial instruction, these tests are limited in their value to support remedial spatial instruction (Cohen & Bairaktarova, 2018). There are several reasons for these limitations.

Many standardized tests that are currently used to screen for spatial ability were developed out of the factor analytic procedure, with the goal of measuring skills that are likely to predict performance in skilled trades and crafts. Consequently, these traditional psychometric spatial ability tests use domain-general stimuli that bear little resemblance to authentic engineering tasks. In addition, these tests lack subscales to identify difficulties faced by students who are challenged by spatial visualization tasks (Cohen & Bairaktarova, 2018).

2 RATIONALE FOR THE WORK

2.1 Application of spatial skills tests

Numerous studies have investigated the relationship between students' demographics, spatial visualization skills, and academic performance. Spatial skills have been linked to abilities to do engineering and technology work, and subsequent studies have provided a relationship between those skills by students and their performance in engineering courses, particularly for engineering graphics and design courses. Additionally, there are reports that indicate the importance of improving spatial visualization skills when looking at students' performance in technology and engineering courses (Kozhevnikov and Thornton, 2006). Other reports indicate the value of improving such skills as the complexity of the problem increases (Titus and Horsman, 2009), which is one of the reason to take a closer look at pre- and post-scores in a standardized test such as Purdue Spatial Visualization Test with Rotations (PSVT:R). The PSVT:R consists of 30 questions with increasing degree of difficulty in terms of number and sequence of spatial rotations that need to be applied to a 3D object in order to end with a desired configuration.

2.2 Predictive analytics

In this study we utilize data analytics, more specifically predictive analytics, which is not commonly used in spatial reasoning research. This type of modelling helps in the identification of factors, i.e., question number or demographic, that have significant impact in the prediction of test score improvement. Predictive analytics is a topic in Data Analytics (DA), which is a generic term used to refer to a set of quantitative and qualitative approaches that are applied to provide the basis for decision making (Rodriguez and Bairaktarova, 2019). Objectives typically pursued when performing modelling with DA techniques are identification of options/factors to increase productivity, boost business profit, or accomplish a given behaviour or performance. Predictive analytics is extensively used in business environments, particularly consumer sciences and where service/ product customization is pursued. It is as well an approach that has gained acceptance in its application to engineering and technology practices, and there have been applications in academic settings, but its application on pedagogical approaches is something novel with high potential.

The software package used in this study is RapidMiner, a commercially available DA software that offers different approaches for the analysis and visualization of datasets, thus allowing comparison of the results, and some level of model optimization. Data analytics techniques help in the identification of dominant factors in a dataset that result in the prediction of a specific performance or behaviour. In this study it means identification of dominant questions in the standardized spatial visualization test and/or demographic parameters, that have a direct positive impact in test score improvement by students. The technique being utilized in this study is Decision-Tree, which has been identified as a good general-purpose algorithm, with acceptable reliability in predictions models. This approach allows for graphical output that is very helpful in envisioning the predictive model that is developed. A decision tree is a collection of nodes in a root-branch sequence that defines selection paths based on specific class or numerical value of selected parameter (e.g., test score). Each node represents a splitting rule for one specific attribute (e.g., answer to a test question). This analytic tool has as well the option to reduce predictive errors by searching for an

optimal decision-tree development, according to a specified criterion (RapidMiner, 2017).

The objective in this study is to search for dominant factors that predict positive test score improvement when comparing pre-intervention to post-intervention evaluation of students' spatial visualization skills. Findings from this study can help in the development of pedagogical approaches with the aim of improving spatial skills. Of interest as well is that results from the predictive models obtained for each subset of data (i.e., pre- and post) will be compared to the results of the predictive model for global score improvement, with the expectation that possible relationships can be established, thus having a more robust pedagogical intervention.

3 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

3.1 Study settings

Data was collected from first-year engineering students in a large public Southeastern university in the United States. A popular spatial visualization test – Purdue Spatial Visualization Test with Rotations (PSVT:R) was administered to the students at the start (pre-) and at the end (post-) of the semester. All participants were enrolled in a one-credit Spatial Visualization course that provides preparation on fundamental spatial skills for an engineering curriculum.

Students are divided in all three sections of the first-year engineering course participated in this study. The course was designed for students with low spatial skills as measured by PSVT: R. Students enrolled in the Spatial Visualization course scored 18 or below (out of 30) on the Purdue Rotation Visualization Test: Revised (PSVT: R) administered to them during summer before their freshman year.

All participants received the same instruction through sixteen weeks-length of the semester, but they were split into three groups, each one having a different set of tools to work on assigned homework. The assigned homework (spatially-related problems) was similar for all three groups, with Group 1 having access to an augmented reality app, Group 2 using a spatial visualization app, and Group 3 utilizing free-hand sketching. The first two groups were required to use the apps for approximately the same time, including time in class and outside of class. Students in the third group were required to do hand sketching activities in class and outside of class, also with roughly the same completion time as for the sections with the apps. Students grades were not affected by using the three different approaches as grading was based on completion only.

All three groups received the same instruction in class through the whole semester. Students in all three groups moved through the course in three modules: 1) sketching, 2) CAD, and 3) 3D object design and creation. During the sketching module, students were introduced to orthographic projection theory, sectional views, and learned how to interpret engineering drawings. During the second module, students learned how to navigate the new user interface and features of the CAD software used in the course (Inventor) and practiced designing simple solids for four weeks. In the final module, all students were introduced in class to additive manufacturing, a step-by-step guide on developing stereolithography (stl) files in order to 3D print each basic solid they designed.

The difference between the three sections was in the methodology that students practiced the above described instruction, and particularly in the rotations of simple solids. During weeks 6 to 16 of the semester, the participants in Group 1 and Group 2 used augmented reality and Spatial Vis apps respectively as part of their class interactive spatial visualization training; Group 3 used sketching techniques. Training time with the apps targeted 40-minutes, starting with 10 minutes in class, followed by 30 minutes required homework time outside of class. Students were graded on completion of and time spent on the tasks.

3.2 Analysis

The complete dataset only consists of valid cases, meaning students that have taken the pre- and the post- tests and received a score. A total of 185 pairs of scores were used in this study, with 89 female and 96 male students participating. The improvement measurement was basically the difference between the students' post- and pre- test (PSVT:R) scores.

Two sets of predictive models were developed, the first set only uses as input improvement in visualization test results, and the second set additionally includes demographic data. The demographic information used in this study is gender, age, and ethnicity. Table 1 provides some basic descriptive statistics for the participants in the dataset.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for dataset.

	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
Number of students	59	66	60
Split Female/Male	27/32	30/36	32/28
Percentage Female	45.76	45.45	53.33
Split Caucasian/Non-C	29/30	35/31	33/27
Percentage Non-Caucasian	50.85	46.97	45.00
Range Age	17 - 19	17 - 19	17 - 23
Age Average & SD	17.86 ± 0.43	18.03 ± 0.34	17.98 ± 0.77

3.3 Improvement measurements

For the evaluation of improvement in performance, we look at the difference between pre- score and post- score for each participant. We utilized three different ways of identifying the difference, as follows:

- a) raw score improvement
- b) percentage improvement
- c) tier indicator of becoming top-scorer.

The first option is the most direct measurement, the post- score minus the prescore, resulting in a valid indicator, however it might misrepresent the actual improvement. For example, a student with low score in the pre-test has more room to get a high increase, which does not imply automatically that it is at the level of topscore. The second option is a popular technique that tries to minimize the effect of raw numbers, percentage improvement, however it might have some bias for the lowscorers since they might show large percentage of improvement but not indicating that the new score is a top-score.

The third option was defined with basis on the ultimate objective of having improved visualization skills in order to have higher possibilities of doing well in a technical field such as engineering. Therefore, it tries to capture if the post- score is good enough to become a top-score. This indicator is the difference between the ‘tier’ were the Post-score is, compared to the ‘tier’ were the Pre-score was. Four tiers were defined in this calculation: Tier 1 – score higher than one Standard Deviation (SD) above average grade for the group; Tier 2 – score between average group score and one SD above; Tier 3 – score between average group score and one SD below; and Tier 4 – score more than one SD below the average group score. Top scores are in Tier 1.

The summary of the improvement indicators for each one of the Groups is given in Table 2. This table gives a better overall picture of the numbers being used under these measurements. These numbers illustrate the existence of students that improved, student that did not improve, and students that showed no variation in their test performance.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for measurements of score improvement

	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
Score Improvement			
Negative	-6	-6	-12
Positive	9	11	10
Average	1.389	2.318	1.830
S.D.	3.600	3.758	3.878
Percentage Improvement			
Negative	-38.46	-42.85	-70.58
Positive	87.5	100	125
Average	12.305	19.375	16.023
S.D.	27.266	30.587	31.448
Tier Improvement			
Negative	-2	-2	-2
Positive	2	2	2
Average	0.084	-0.196	0.067
S.D.	0.794	0.808	0.806

4 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Predictive models

The aim is to identify factors in the PSVT:R test that are most influential in predicting score improvement. The predictive models for improved performance yielded multi-level decision trees, with all of them with at least three levels (Figure 1).

Decision Tree - Model

Figure 1. Decision tree for predictive model – Group 1, raw score.

4.2 Summary for groups

The results in terms of the identified most dominant factor that serves main predictor of performance are summarized in Table 3. It can be observed that in all three groups the models have a primary predictive factor that is in the middle of the test (Q13 to Q16), which implies a degree of difficulty in the question that is not the easiest one or the hardest one. Even at the second level, most of the predictive factors are as well in the middle of the test, with the few different cases having as factors a harder question and an easier question (e.g. Q28/Q9 in Group 3). This situation is related to the specific branch where these factors are utilized, remembering that one branch is for positive outcome of the improvement indicator, and the other branch is for a negative outcome.

Table 3. Main predictors of performance – question number.

Only Q's	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
Score Improvement			
Level 1	Q15	Q16	Q13
Level 2	Q14/Q9	Q21/Q4	Q4/Q14
Percentage Improvement			
Level 1	Q15	Q16	Q13
Level 2	Q11/Q9	Q21/Q4	Q16/Q19
Tier Improvement			
Level 1	Q14	Q16	Q21
Level 2	Q28/Q9	Q10/Q13	Q13/Q14

Regarding the degree of difficulty in the test, the middle questions are related to questions where two rotations are required to get to the correct answer. All primary factors identified are in this region. There are some cases for secondary factors (Level 2), indicated with colored background in the table, where the dominant factor belongs to different degree of difficulty, with the blue background indicating one more degree of difficulty, and the brown background with more significant change in the degree of difficulty.

5 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Improvement of spatial visualization skills were analysed in this study. A group of first-year engineering students were tested and three different pedagogical interventions were utilized. Based on the analyses performed, there is no significant difference among the three groups regarding performance. Furthermore, predictive models are consistent on defining dominant factors of average degree of difficulty, with identification of the same factors for the raw and percentage improvement indicators. Lastly, our findings suggest that demographics variables are not primary influential factors for performance, and therefore for prediction; these factors do have a secondary (minor) role.

Applying data analytics techniques in our study, confirmed previous results for single-instance test scores and identified influential factors in a predictive model. The results show a level of similarity, but not full agreement or consistency, which is expected. This study demonstrates the usefulness of data analytics in this type of analyses. The identification of influential factors (i.e., specific test questions) in a

predictive model for score improvement can aid in defining the content needed in pedagogical interventions and provide a new perspective in the field of engineering education, and specifically in the development and enhancement of spatial skills of engineering students.

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